
Analysis of Wind Flow Around a Curved Building with GASCANS

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Abstract

This paper looks at the efficacy of the Lattice Boltzmann method (LBM) based GPU-accelerated solver for coupled approaches to Navier Stokes (GASCANS) developed at The University of Manchester to numerically model the flow around a complex curved building such as a curved dome. The airflow around a 1:54 scale model of a domed structure in a fully developed atmospheric boundary layer is simulated. The LBM results were validated using experimental data and numerical results from Rahmatmand et al.(2014) [5]. GASCANS produces accurate results compared to experiment data, but has some discrepancies. Flow features such as flow separation and recirculation are not accurately predicted. A higher grid resolution, addition of wall functions and introduction of turbulence at the inlet might help in improving the accuracy of results.

Keywords : Lattice Boltzmann method; Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes;GPU-accelerated solver for coupled approaches to Navier Stokes(GASCANS);Large Eddy Simulation;Synthetic Eddy Method

1 Introduction

CFD modelling is an excellent way to visualise and analyse flow around structures in an urban environment. Understanding flow around buildings in cities is important for cost-effective construction, structural integrity, aerodynamic shape optimization, decreased vortex induced vibrations, passive cooling, pedestrian comfort, pollutant dispersion and urban wind energy production. [2] [5]

Mehdi N Bahadori [1] explored the passive cooling techniques used in Iranian architecture. Notably, the use of wind towers, fountains and underground streams to aid cooling of buildings. Passive cooling techniques are more important than ever before to achieve net zero emissions or to reduce emissions contributed by air conditioning systems. To ensure the efficient working of these passive cooling systems, it is essential to study the airflow around buildings in focus, as the shape of the structure and the openings such as windows affects the flow around it. In countries like Iran, dome shaped roof have been developed over the centuries and have proved to be quite effective in keeping buildings cool during the hot summer days and warm during cool summer nights. These structures have open apertures on the roof and windows and doors on the sides. The presence of these openings affects the airflow within the structure and around it compared to a closed dome.

Numerical modelling of fluid flow is commonly performed by solving Navier Stokes equations with appropriate boundary conditions. In this method, a computational domain is divided into multiple cells which could be structured or unstructured, and a set of governing equations are solved iteratively to obtain flow data. All turbulence length scales could be captured using Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS), only the largest relevant features could be captured using Large Eddy

Simulation (LES) or the flow could be completely modelled using Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) to obtain a time averaged results without instantaneous flow information. All three methods have their own advantages and limitations and depending on the requirements, a viable one could be selected. High-fidelity Navier Stokes solvers require powerful CPUs, take a long time to produce results and are complicated to run on multiple CPU cores. Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) is an alternative to Navier Stokes solvers. In LBM, fluid particles move in fixed directions in the lattice where they stream and collide, ensuring conservation of mass and momentum. Macroscopic fluid properties such as density and velocity are obtained by summing up these distribution functions in different directions in the lattice. Boundary conditions such as slip, no slip, uniform gradient and periodic can be used. In addition to this, Immersed Boundary Condition allows to model flow over complex objects and also fluid structure interaction (FSI) through coupling with a Finite Element solver. This boundary condition has not been implemented in the current study. When implemented, this could improve accuracy of flow over curved surfaces compared to the no slip or bounceback boundary condition.

GASCANS is a numerical solver developed at the University of Manchester which uses a BGK LBM-LES solver to run time-dependent simulations cost-effectively on GPUs. Thus, the solver resolves large to medium turbulence scales at a fraction of the computation cost required for DNS. The LES Smagorinsky turbulence model is employed to model the smallest eddy scales. This allows coarser mesh to be used with a minor compromise in accuracy. As GPUs are commonly available on consumer devices nowadays, and hence reasonably accurate and well resolved flow simulations can be performed at a consumer level. When coupled with a NS solver, turbulence can be incorporated into the inlet of LBM domain using a SEM model with mean turbulence values from the NS solver. In this study, this feature is not enabled and only a mean velocity profile without turbulence is used at the inlet boundary. Compared to NS solver, LBM solvers use more memory and regular cell size limit number of cells and accuracy of the results. However, LBM algorithm is easy to code and run on GPUs. GASCANS uses 3D point cloud data in the form of x, y and z coordinates to form the input geometry within the domain. A 3DQ19 lattice is utilised in GASCANS. [2]

Camps Santasmasas, M. et al., [3] validates results from GASCANS with various test cases such as turbulent channel flow, flow around Ahmed body, rigid cylinder and moving plate. The test cases achieved a close accuracy with experimental results and NS solvers. However, the research work recommends a better boundary cell treatment to improve accuracy. Camps Santasmasas, M. et al., [4] discusses two nested and coupled numerical models where a LB-LES and a NS-LES domain are nested inside a larger RANS domain. Both these models were used to simulate flow around a rectangular building within an atmospheric boundary layer. It was found that both these models predict flow well and match with experimental results. Furthermore, the amount this work shows that LB-LES was 25 times computationally cheaper relative to the NS-LES approach. Hence, more grid cells can be employed to resolve small flow features relative to NS solvers and yet achieve accurate results faster.

Wijesooriya et al., [6] presented an in-depth literature review of the different approaches taken to visualise flow around tall structures. They discussed advantages and limitations of CFD modelling methods such as RANS, LES and DNS. While conducting experiments or CFD, they emphasise that the inlet flow conditions representing the atmospheric boundary layer plays crucial role in producing accurate results. To capture all scales of motion, a well refined grid is required where there are fine cells close to the object in the wall boundary layer and the cells extending away may be coarser. This ensures more cells in the region of interest and reduces the total number of cells and thus reducing computational power required to run the simulations. They also compare the efficacy of cell shapes such as hexahedral, tetrahedral and polyhedral. They also mention that the y^+ values must be less than 1 close to the walls for curved surfaces to accurately model the

boundary layer. However, y^+ value could be higher than 30 if wall functions are used. They go on to discuss FSI of flow on tall buildings and aerodynamic optimization of structures to minimize vortex induced vibrations. The impact of how flow around tall buildings could affect the flow around neighbouring buildings as is the case in a city was also looked at. Finally, relatively latest CFD method LBM, is discussed along with potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in simulation of wind in urban environments.

This paper focuses on evaluating the accuracy of GASCANS in modelling flow around curved objects as present literature does not emphasise on curved objects. For this purpose, a closed aperture curved dome was chosen. Rahmatmand et al., [5] conducted an experimental and a RANS based numerical study of airflow around a dome-shaped building when present inside an atmospheric boundary layer. They used a 1:54 scaled-down model with a base diameter of 0.11m and a height of 0.127m. The Reynolds number based on the freestream velocity 15m/s was around 1.22×10^5 . The velocity profiles and streamlines along the streamwise direction at the mid plane of the domain showed a couple of recirculation zones. The curved dome shape has a clear effect on the airflow around it. As the dome shape curves down from the roof, reversed flow was observed at multiple locations and consequently flow detached from the surface. Due to the huge velocity gradients, turbulence was generated in the aft of the dome. They also observed two recirculation zones in the wake of the dome in case of the closed dome and only one of the same in case of the dome with open apertures. For the numerical simulation, they employed a finite volume method with upwind discretization and a SIMPLE based solver with RNG $\kappa - \epsilon$ model for turbulence modelling. The numerical results were found to be fairly matching the experimental data. However, there were minor differences in the flow behind the dome reproduced by the numerical model compared to the experimental results. The present study uses GASCANS to model flow around a closed dome and validate the results with Rahmatmand et al., [5]. Moreover, this work is one of the initial studies that focus on flow around a curved body using GASCANS.

(a) Dimensions of scaled-down geometry [5]

(b) CAD geometry created in CATIA V5

Figure 1: Geometry details

2 Methodology

GASCANS is a GPU-accelerated software that utilises the Lattice Boltzmann Method to numerically model fluid flow inside a computational domain having an embedded geometry. The CAD geometry in STL format was converted to a point cloud file using MATLAB script provided by Dr Marta Camps Santasmasas. This point cloud file was then stored in the ‘input’ folder in GASCANS directory. The grid resolution, timestep, boundary conditions, inlet velocity profile, domain size, total timesteps, time averaging start time and output file writing frequency could be adjusted by changing parameters in input folder. Also, the geometry can be scaled in x, y or z directions and its position in the geometry can be changed easily. Grid resolutions of 100, 200, 400 and 600 were employed in this study and the corresponding cell sizes were 1/100, 1/200, 1/400 and 1/600. The ability to use higher resolution grids were limited by available GPU memory.

Figure 2: Computational domain

The dimensions of the dome placed in the wind tunnel is displayed in Figure 1a. It shows a dome with several windows and an aperture opening at the top. For this project, all these openings are assumed to be closed. The geometry for this project shown in Figure 1b was created in CATIA V5 using the layout in Figure 1a.

The computational domain along with the dimensions used in this project can be seen in Figure 2. The domain size was 1.4m in x direction, 0.577m in y direction and 0.225m in z direction. The centre of the closed dome is located 0.35m from the inlet and 0.225m away from the side wall. The centre of the dome is considered the origin and the positive values is along the flow direction.

The figures 3a and 3b show the close up view of the dome for 400 and 600 grid resolution respectively. Due the regular lattice grid generated by GASCANS, a “staircase” like pattern is created over the curved surface of the dome. This could potentially introduce errors in the results when used with bounce-back boundary condition. Turbulence was not added to the inlet velocity. The inlet velocity profile was generated by using power law :

$$\frac{u}{U_{ref}} = \left(\frac{y}{H_{ref}}\right)^{0.28} \quad \dots Eq(1)$$

where H_{ref} is 400 millimetre or 0.4 metres and U_{ref} is 15m/s

(a) 400 resolution

(b) 400 resolution

Figure 3: Geometry details

The results were obtained in HDF5 file format and imported to Paraview for postprocessing. Velocity contours and streamlines were generated using Paraview. Line plots were generated using MATLAB scripts. The table 1 shows the boundary conditions of the computation domain.

Domain region	Boundary condition
Inlet	Fixed velocity
Outlet	Zero velocity gradient
Ground	Slip
Top	No slip
Side faces	periodic

Table 1: Boundary conditions.

The Figure 4a displays a comparison between the inlet velocity used in the experiment and the velocity profile generated by using power law using Eq (1). The power law perfectly matches with the experiment. A comparison between inlet velocity profiles used in the experiment and GASCANS cases with 400 and 600 grid resolutions is shown in the Figure 4b. Again, we can confirm that the velocity profiles coincide each other well. Therefore, the inlet boundary conditions match for the experiment and GASCANS cases.

2.1 Time Convergence Study

Figures 5a and 5b represent a comparison between velocity profiles at $x/H_{ref} = 0$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.163$ for multiple timesteps with experimental and numerical results from Rahmatmand et al. [5]. (Initial timesteps of 200000 and 5000000 have been ignored here). We can observe that the numerical results from GASCANS do not change significantly from 400000 to 2000000 timestep. Apart from smoother velocity profiles due to more grid cells, like in the 400 grid resolution case, the increase in timesteps does not produce more accurate results for 600 grid resolution. However, there is a mismatch between the results from this project and Rahmatmand et al. [5] as seen in Figure 5a and Figure 5b. From $y/H_{ref} = 0$ to 0.225, GASCANS underpredicts the flow velocity compared to

(a) Inlet velocity profile generated using power law (b) Velocity profile applied to 400 and 600 resolution cases

Figure 4: Inlet velocity profile comparison

values from the research paper. Beyond $y/H_{ref} = 0.225$, GASCANS overpredicts the flow velocity. However, in the same region, RANS simulation matches well with LBM results. This shows that the numerical models of RANS and LBM are unable to capture flow features accurately.

Figure 5: Comparison of velocity profiles vertically at $x/H_{ref} = 0$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.163$

2.2 Mesh Convergence Study

Figure 6, compares three different grid resolutions for grid independence. Values on the y axis are the normalised values of change in streamwise velocity for each grid resolution. Grid resolution of 100 was ignored as it was too coarse and did not produce satisfactory results. We can observe a decreasing trend in the difference between time averaged streamwise velocity values observed at x

Figure 6: Grid resolution study. Values taken at $x = 0.35\text{m}$, $y = 0.1\text{m}$ and $z = 0.1598\text{m}$

$= 0.35\text{m}$, $y = 0.1\text{m}$ and $z = 0.1598\text{m}$. This shows the grid is moving towards grid independence. However, grid independence can not be fully confirmed as we do not have results from a higher resolution grid due to limitation of computation facilities. Therefore, the results from 600 grid resolution and 2 million timesteps would be considered mainly for further analysis.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 7 shows non dimensionalised, scaled down velocity profiles at various locations on the mid plane of the domain for 600 resolution grid. $x/H_{ref} = 0$ is taken as the centre of the dome and x direction is from left to right. The solid lines represent results obtained from the present numerical analysis and the dots are experimental values. For the streamwise positions in the upstream, apart from velocity profile at $x/H_{ref} = -0.262$, the velocity profiles at $x/H_{ref} = -0.237$ and -0.187 matches experiment well. Close to the apex surface, where flow separation occurs, the velocity profiles are underpredicted. However, as one moves away from the dome surface, accuracy is retained. In the wake of the dome, Rahmatmand et al. [5] observes two points of zero velocity for profiles at $x/H_{ref} = 0.187$ and beyond. However, GASCANS only predicts one point of zero velocity along these profiles.

Figures 8a and 8b provides a comparison of normalised streamwise velocity profiles along two different vertical lines close to the dome for the 600 grid resolution and 2000000 timestep. A comparison of streamwise velocity at $x/H_{ref} = 0.075$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.155$ with experimental and numerical results from Rahmatmand et al. [5] is shown in Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3 shows the same comparison at $x/H_{ref} = 0$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.163$. The case with 600 grid resolution performs the best and matches better to the experiment compared to other grid resolutions. Keeping this in mind, below $y/H_{ref} = 0.2$, GASCANS underperforms significantly and above $y/H_{ref} = 0.4$, it matches more closely with RANS simulations than experimental data. However, this is the most accurate results GASCANS was able to produce using available computational resources and solver settings. It is evident that GASCANS finds it difficult to reproduce flow features close to the wall boundary of the dome. Grid refinement close to wall boundary or usage of immersive boundary method could improve present results.

Figure 7: Comparison of scaled velocity profiles at different locations along the mid plane

(a) at $x/H_{ref} = 0.075$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.155$

(b) at $x/H_{ref} = 0$ and $z/H_{ref} = -0.163$

Figure 8: Streamwise velocity profiles

Figure 9 displays the velocity streamlines on a plane parallel to xz plane at $y/H_{ref} = 0.166$ which is overlapped by a streamwise velocity contour. As the boundary layer develops, the incoming flow accelerates over the curved surface of the dome and a recirculation zone can be observed behind the dome. The flow accelerates due to a negative pressure gradient and beyond a point the flow starts to decelerate as the momentum of the flow reduces. This leads to a positive pressure gradient which causes flow separation and a turbulent wake region is produced.

Streamlines at the midplane where $z/H_{ref} = 0$ is shown in figure 10. Due to the curved surface, the flow accelerates in this plane as well. The flow separates close to the apex of the dome and a recirculation zone is formed in the wake of the flow. The flow reattaches the ground at around $x/H_{ref} = 0.583$. A small recirculation region is seen close to the ground behind the dome. Figure

Figure 9: Velocity streamlines at $y/H_{ref} = 0.166$

Figure 10: Velocity streamlines at mid plane

11 shows the streamlines from Rahmatmand et al., [5]. In comparison to GASCANS, streamlines produced by RANS simulation from [5] shows two recirculation zones - a small region close to the apex of the dome and a larger one in the wake of the dome. GASCANS does not produce the recirculation zone at the apex accurately. This could be the reason why velocity profiles do not match well with experimental data in this region. Also, the shape and the exact location of the larger zone produced by GASCANS is different from that of the RANS simulation. The recirculation zone is closer to the apex as produced by GASCANS and the same is closer to the ground for RANS simulation.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, a GPU-accelerated LBM solver GASCANS was used to numerically model the wind flow around a scaled down model of a closed dome placed in an atmospheric boundary layer. A grid independence and timestep study were performed with multiple cases with varying grid resolutions and timesteps. MATLAB and Paraview were employed for postprocessing. Streamwise velocity contours, line plots and streamlines were generated and analysed. GASCANS does produce accurate results far away from the geometry in focus. However, close to the object, it was unable to capture the flowfield similar to the experiment conducted by Rahmatmand et al., [5]. This could be due to insufficient cells to resolve the flow features well. Two recirculation zones were observed behind the building- a large one close to the apex of the dome and a smaller one close to the ground. The separated flow from the dome reattaches the ground at around $x/H_{ref} = 0.583$ from the centre of the dome. GASCANS struggle to capture a small recirculation zone close to the apex of the

Figure 11: Streamlines on the mid plane [5]

dome, which is produced by RANS simulation and also the flow details within this region. Overall, discrepancies in flow features produced by GASCANS are located close to regions with high velocity gradients.

A higher grid resolution with finer cells would need to be tested for grid independence and accuracy of results even though the ‘staircase’ like feature would still exist. The ‘staircase’ feature in the grid can be eliminated through local refinement. Wall functions could play a crucial role in modelling boundary layer more accurately. Introducing turbulence at the inlet could also improve the accuracy of results from GASCANS. Alternatively, the Immersed Boundary Method boundary condition could be employed at curved boundaries for better results. The total timesteps would need not be significantly increased for a higher grid resolution as current 400 and 600 grid resolutions do not show variation with more total timesteps.

Acknowledgments

The author is incredibly grateful to Dr Marta Camps Santasmasas, Research Associate at the University of Manchester, for her excellent guidance, support and constructive feedback through weekly meetings throughout the completion of this project. The author also thank her for providing access to GASCANS software and running simulation cases on the University of Manchester computational facility. In addition, the author would like to thank Dr Alistair Revell, Professor of Computational Engineering at the University of Manchester, for his guidance which led to this project.

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